

1 **Effect of E-beam treatment on the expression of virulence and stress-response genes**
2 **of *Listeria monocytogenes* in dry-cured ham**

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13

14 **Abstract**

15 In response to stress, *Listeria monocytogenes* cells surviving adverse conditions trigger
16 protective mechanisms that can increase their virulence. The objective of this work was
17 to evaluate the expression of stress-response (*sigB*) and three virulence (*plcA*, *hly* and
18 *iap*) genes of *L. monocytogenes* sublethally injured by the application of E-beam
19 treatment to dry-cured ham. For that, slices of this product were contaminated with *L.*
20 *monocytogenes* S4-2 and irradiated with 1, 2 and 3 kGy. After treatment, samples were
21 stored at different temperatures (7 and 15°C) for 30 days. Gene expression and number of
22 *Listeria* survivors were determined by RT-qPCR and microbial counts, respectively, at
23 different times (0, 7, 15 and 30 days) during storage. Both stress response and virulence
24 genes showed a significantly increased Gene Expression Rate (GER, log gene
25 copies/(cfu/g)) according with the dose applied, being higher at 3 kGy. During storage,
26 GER of all genes studied followed an increasing trend but there was only a significant
27 effect of time on those irradiated with 3 kGy ($p \leq 0.05$). No significant influence of storage
28 temperature was observed ($p > 0.05$).

29 **Key words:** Cured meat products, pathogenic microorganisms, radiation, Gene
30 Expression Rate.

31 1. Introduction

32 *Listeria monocytogenes* is a ubiquitous microorganism disseminated in widely different
33 habitats, such as the cytosol of living host cells and the surfaces of food processing
34 environments (Gandhi and Chikindas, 2007, Buchanan et al., 2017). This microorganism
35 causes listeriosis, a disease that usually occurs as an imperceptible infection but can cause
36 serious problems in humans with weakened immune systems, i.e. newborns,
37 immunocompromised, pregnant women and the elderly. In this high-risk group, *L.*
38 *monocytogenes* can lead to severe clinical conditions such as septicaemia, gastroenteritis,
39 abortions, meningitis and encephalitis (Lecuit, 2007, Lamont et al., 2011). Therefore,
40 although the incidence rate of listeriosis is lower compare to other foodborne diseases, it
41 has a high mortality rate estimated at 20-30% (Hunt et al., 2018). This pathogen is
42 possibly the one that most concerns the food industry, health authorities and consumers
43 because it is widely distributed in the agri-food industry environments and its main route
44 of transmission to humans is precisely through food, especially ready-to-eat foods
45 (Ferreira et al., 2014). Although food raw materials may contain *L. monocytogenes*, the
46 main contamination comes from the surfaces of food processing facilities, due to this
47 pathogen's ability to produce biofilms and persist for prolonged periods in these
48 environments (Hoelzer et al., 2015). As a result, *Listeria* often cross-contaminates food
49 during post-production processes such as slicing, cutting or packaging (Morganti et al.,
50 2016, Buchanan et al., 2017).

51 Moreover, *L. monocytogenes* can grow in different types of food even when stored at
52 refrigeration temperatures (0-5°C) and also resists several stress conditions (low pH and
53 a_w , high salt concentration or antimicrobial and disinfectant agents) which are frequently
54 used for food preservation since normally hinder or inhibit the growth of other bacteria
55 (Gandhi and Chikindas, 2007, Rolhion and Cossart, 2017, Buchanan et al., 2017). This
56 unique ability to survive stressful environments is the result of its genetic adaptation that,
57 through complex pathways, allows this pathogen to control the stress-response and
58 virulence genes expression (Gandhi and Chikindas, 2007, Miner et al., 2007, Bucur et al.,
59 2018). The regulation of these genes' expression is also a *sine qua non* for the success of
60 the *L. monocytogenes* infection process of their living hosts (Rolhion and Cossart, 2017,
61 Vázquez-Boland et al., 2001).

62 Most of the genetic mechanisms that confer this exceptional tolerance and also favour its
63 intestinal adaptation are mainly regulated by the alternative sigma factor (σ^B), encoded by
64 *sigB* gene (Toledo-Arana et al., 2009). Among the main virulence factors of *L.*
65 *monocytogenes* include listeriolysin O, a haemolysin pore-forming protein, and the
66 phosphatidylinositol-specific phospholipase C, encoded by *hly* and *plcA* genes,
67 respectively. These proteins are required to lysate the phagosome membrane and allow it
68 to escape into the cell cytoplasm, a crucial step in the *Listeria* cell invasion (Goldfine and
69 Marquis, 2007, Pushkareva and Ermolaeva, 2010). Another essential factor is the
70 autolysin P60 (the invasion-associated protein), encoded by *iap* gene, that is involved in
71 the cell invasion and intracellular motility process of *L. monocytogenes* (Pucciarelli et al.,
72 2007, Pilgrim et al., 2003).

73 The different environmental conditions present in food matrices can cause variations in
74 the expression of *sigB*, *plcA*, *hly* and *iap* genes, which often lead to an increase in their
75 expression (Rantsiou et al., 2012, Alía et al., 2019). In this way, several authors reported
76 changes in the expression of these genes when *L. monocytogenes* was exposed to some
77 sublethal conditions as low pH and a_w in some food products (Olesen et al., 2009, Bae et
78 al., 2012, Walecka-Zacharska et al., 2013, Mataragas et al., 2015).

79 Dry-cured ham is a meat product with increasing worldwide demand, especially for its
80 more consumer-friendly boned and sliced formats. As mentioned above, boning and
81 slicing result in additional handling that entails the risk contamination with pathogens
82 such as *L. monocytogenes*. Although dry-cured ham is a hostile environment for listerial
83 growth because of its low a_w and high salt concentration, this microorganism could
84 remain in the product pending more favourable conditions. This significant health risk
85 justifies that some countries, e.g. the USA, have implemented the “tolerance zero”
86 criterion for *L. monocytogenes* in ready-to-eat foods. Consequently, it means an impact
87 on the commercialization of products such as dry-cured ham. Thus, it is necessary to
88 apply treatments to eliminate this pathogen without compromising the final quality of the
89 product. It is well known from some previous works (Hoz et al., 2008, Lucas et al., 2020)
90 that the E-beam irradiation, a non-thermal technology, reduces *L. monocytogenes* in this
91 meat product to achieve “tolerance zero” standards.

92 To date, the effect of the E-beam irradiation on the expression of stress-response and
93 virulence genes of *L. monocytogenes* survivors remains unknown. This is important

94 because the possible spread of *L. monocytogenes* with an enhanced expression of these
95 genes could indicate a virulence increase and consequently, to represent a higher public
96 health hazard. Therefore, this study aims to know the expression of stress-response (*sigB*)
97 and three virulence (*plcA*, *hly* and *iap*) genes of this pathogen sublethally injured by the
98 application of E-beam treatment to dry-cured ham.

99 **2. Materials and methods**

100 **2.1. *Listeria monocytogenes* culture preparation**

101 *Listeria monocytogenes* S4-2 (serotype 1/2b) was used for this experiment due to its
102 higher radioresistance on dry-cured ham than other *Listeria* spp. serotypes isolated from
103 meat industry, as tested in a previous work (Lucas et al., 2020). Fresh cultures were
104 prepared by adding a small portion of a lyophilized stock culture to Trypticase Soy Broth
105 (TSB) (Oxoid, Basingstoke, England) and incubated at 32°C for 24 h. Then, two
106 successive subcultures were performed inoculating 0.1 ml of the 24-h-culture into 9 ml of
107 TSB and incubating at 32°C for 24 h. Finally, the culture was centrifuged at 13500 x g
108 for 30 min at 5°C in a Sorvall RC-5B centrifuge (Du Pont instruments, USA). The pellets
109 were resuspended in 50 ml of sterile saline solution (0.85% NaCl), obtaining a cell
110 suspension that used to contaminate the dry-cured ham samples.

111 **2.2. Contamination of the dry-cured ham slices and E-beam treatment**

112 Dry-cured hams slices of approximately 10 g were obtained using an electric slicer
113 machine (Beckers ES 300, Treviglio, Italy) from a Spanish product marketed in vacuum
114 packaging, deboned, ripened for 11 months, and with a_w values ranging from 0.88 to 0.89
115 and a salt content of 5 g/100 g. These slices were contaminated by immersion for 10
116 seconds in the *Listeria* suspension previously obtained with a high number of listeria (ca.
117 8 log cfu/g) in order to study the evolution over time of both microorganisms and gene
118 expression. The contaminated slices were individually vacuum-packaged (20 kPa) into
119 polyethylene plastic bags of low gas permeability (35 and 150 cm³/ 24h m² bars for O₂
120 and CO₂, respectively). These samples were transported in insulated polystyrene boxes at
121 4°C to the IONISOS Ibérica (Tarancón, Spain) irradiation facility equipped with an
122 industrial E-beam radiation source which operates at 10 MeV.

123 The samples were irradiated at different doses: 1, 2 and 3 kGy. Non-treated samples were
124 used as control (0 kGy). During E-beam treatment, the increase of temperature in the

125 samples was less than 2°C. The dose absorbed by the slices was checked by absorbance
126 measurement (280 nm) of simultaneously irradiated cellulose triacetate dosimeters placed
127 on the bags surface (ASTM, 2013). Finally, the samples were transferred to the
128 laboratory. Half of the samples were stored at 7°C and the other half at 15°C, values
129 selected according to CRL/AFSSA (2008) as temperature abuse during food storage at
130 the level of food business operators, retail and consumer. *L. monocytogenes* counts and
131 gene expression analysis were performed immediately after treatment and at 7, 15 and 30
132 days of storage.

133 **2.4. Microbiological analyses**

134 To count the survivors, the slices were homogenized with sterile saline solution in a
135 Stomacher Mix2 (AES Laboratoire, Combourg, France). The counts were performed by
136 the pour-plate method using Palcam Agar (CM0877) added with antibiotic supplement
137 (polymyxin B, acriflavine HCl and ceftazimide; SR0150E) and yolk egg emulsion
138 (SR0047) (Oxoid, Basingstoke, England). The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 h and
139 the colonies were enumerated with a colony counter Digital S (Selecta, Barcelona,
140 Spain). Counts were performed in triplicate and the results were expressed in log cfu/g.
141 The remaining homogenates were transferred to 50 ml centrifuge tubes (Falcon®) and
142 frozen at -80°C until further analysis.

143 **2.5. RNA extraction**

144 The samples stored at -80°C were thawed in refrigeration (4°C). The RNA was extracted
145 using the MasterPure™ RNA Purification Kit (Epicentre, Wisconsin, USA). For that, 1
146 ml of thawed sample was centrifuged in microtubes of 1.5 ml at 4°C at 10621 x g in an
147 Eppendorf microcentrifuge 5430 R (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The supernatant
148 was carefully removed, and the pellet was resuspended in 300 µl of a cell lysis solution (1
149 µl of 50 µg/µl Proteinase K in 300 µl of Tissue and Cell Lysis Solution). The mixture
150 was incubated at 65°C for 15 minutes and placed on ice for 5 minutes. Then, 300 µl of
151 chloroform was added and centrifuged again; this step was incorporate to discard the dry-
152 cured ham fat. Approximately 200 µl of the supernatant was mixed with 175 µl of the
153 MPC protein precipitation reagent and centrifuged as described above. Supernatant
154 containing genetic material was mixed with 500 µl of 99.5% isopropanol (Thermo Fisher
155 Scientific, New Jersey, USA) and stored at -20°C for 20-30 min before centrifuging as
156 described. The pellet obtained was resuspended in 200 µl of the DNAsa solution and

157 incubated at 37°C for 15 min. Tissue and cell lysis solution (200 µl) and protein
158 precipitation detergent (200 µl) were added and then centrifuged as described. Finally,
159 500 µl isopropanol was added to the supernatant and centrifuged again. The resulting
160 pellet containing RNA was washed with 200 µl of 70% ethanol and resuspended at 35 µl
161 of the TE buffer (10 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8).

162 The RNA suspension (1 µl) was placed in the NanoDrop 2000c spectrophotometer
163 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, New Jersey, USA) and the absorbance was determined at 260
164 and 280 nm to verify the RNA concentration and purity, respectively. The RNA
165 concentration was normalized to 25-50 ng/µl and frozen at -80°C for further analysis.

166 **2.6. *plcA*, *hly*, *iap* and *sigB* gene expression**

167 Analysis of target gene expression was performed using RT-qPCR in two steps, i.e. the
168 complementary DNA (cDNA) was synthesized from the RNA extracted by reverse
169 transcription reaction (RT) and then the cDNA was used in the qPCR reaction.

170 The cDNA was produced using the PrimeScrip™ Reagent kit Perfect Real Time (Takara,
171 Shiga, Japan). For that, a mixture of 5 µl of the kit reagent mixture and 5 µl of the
172 previously normalized RNA was placed in a PCR thermocycler AG 22331 (Eppendorf,
173 Hamburg, Germany) and subjected to 37°C for 15 min followed by 85°C for 5 s. A blank
174 containing 5 µl of water instead of RNA was included in each assay. The cDNA to be
175 used as target for real-time PCR (qPCR) was stored at -20°C for further analysis.

176 According to the protocol described by Alía et al. (2019), the expression of the *plcA*, *hly*,
177 *iap* and *sigB* genes were estimated by qPCR from the cDNA and the corresponding
178 primers using the ViiA™ 7 Real Time PCR System and ViiA™ 7 V.1.2.2 software
179 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, New Jersey, USA). As described by Hoorgar et al. (2003), the
180 16S-23S rRNA intergenic spacer (IGS) region was also amplified as constitutive or
181 “normalizer” gene to assure appropriateness of RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis
182 processes. Gene expression of each sample was evaluated in triplicate.

183 The results were expressed as the Gene Expression Rate (GER) defined as the logarithm
184 of the ratio of the number of gene copies and *Listeria* survivors: GER = Log [gene
185 copies/ (cfu/g)].

186 **2.7. Statistical analysis**

187 The Shapiro–Wilk test was performed to determine the normality of the data. Analysis of
188 variance (ANOVA) and Tukey’s multiple comparison were used to determine the
189 individual effect of the dose, temperature and time of storage on GER of each target gene
190 (*sigB*, *plcA*, *hly* and *iap*) and also on microbiological counts. Analyses were done using
191 IBM SPSS Statistics v23.0 software for Windows (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). Survival
192 equations, coefficients of determination (R^2 values) of the curves, *D*-value and the F-test
193 were calculated using Excel (Microsoft, Redmond, Washington, USA). Statistical
194 significance was established at $p \leq 0.05$.

195 **3. Results and discussion**

196 Table 1 shows the listeria behaviour in both un-treated (0 kGy) and treated (1, 2 and 3
197 kGy) samples during storage at 7°C. As expected, as the E-beam dose increased, the
198 numbers of *L. monocytogenes* decreased following first-order inactivation kinetics. From
199 data corresponding to day 0, a *D*-value of 0.57 kGy was calculated, which is very similar
200 to that previously determined for dry-cured ham and other meat products (Lucas et al.,
201 2020, Sommers and Mackay, 2013). Therefore, it is confirmed that E-beam dose of 2
202 kGy would be sufficient to sanitize the dry-cured ham (Lucas et al., 2020).

203 During the storage at 7°C, the *L. monocytogenes* counts of both untreated and treated
204 samples slightly declined as the time elapsed, with no significant differences ($p > 0.05$)
205 attributable to E-beam treatment. Thus, the death rate due to the environmental conditions
206 of the ham (mainly the high salt concentration, the nitrate content and the low a_w) is
207 higher, and therefore hinders, that produced by the sublethal damage of the radiation.

208 The same pattern was observed in samples stored at 15°C (data not shown). Similarly,
209 Montiel et al. (2020) reported that the environmental conditions of dry-cured ham could
210 reduce the load of *L. monocytogenes* by at least 4.6 log units on the surface of this
211 product.

212 Fig. 1 shows GER values (mean \pm SD) of *sigB*, *plcA*, *hly* and *iap* genes of *L.*
213 *monocytogenes* in dry-cured ham slices untreated (0 kGy) and treated (1, 2 and 3 kGy)
214 and stored during 30 days at different temperatures (7 and 15°C). For all cases, this
215 parameter increased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) as the irradiation dose increased. The results
216 indicate that E-beam treatment survivors would respond by overexpressing these genes in
217 a relevant way that, in turn, would be an indicator of their higher virulence. This

218 behaviour could be a consequence of the adaptative response of *L. monocytogenes* to
219 overcome the E-beam injury at cellular level.

220 After exposure to E-beam, microbial growth is inhibited through two main mechanisms
221 which occur simultaneously and cause cell death when the extent of the damage exceeds
222 its repair capacity (Huang et al., 2019). One mechanism is the direct interaction of
223 accelerated electrons with some vital macromolecules such as DNA and RNA, and the
224 second is the indirect action of reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by water
225 radiolysis, which contributes to oxidative damage of nucleic acid, protein and enzyme. In
226 fact, the radiation survival of bacteria is determined by the DNA repair mechanism and
227 their ROS-scavenging capacity (Slade and Radman, 2011). Therefore, *L. monocytogenes*
228 cells surviving to E-beam treatment have been subjected to a high oxidative stress. To
229 withstand oxidative damage is not entirely unknown to this microorganism. In fact, it has
230 been reported that *L. monocytogenes* frequently develops several molecular mechanisms
231 to overcome the exposure to oxidizing compounds inside macrophages (Imlay, 2002,
232 Lungu et al., 2009). This situation, as in most stresses, triggers the general stress response
233 mechanism of *L. monocytogenes* controlled by *sigB* (Bucur et al., 2018). Several studies
234 have demonstrated the role of alternative sigma factor (σ^B) in the *L. monocytogenes*
235 oxidative resistance either because there are σ^B -dependent genes implied in the resistance
236 to this stress (Kazmierczak et al., 2003, Raengpradub et al., 2008, Hecker et al., 2007) or
237 because mutant microorganisms lacking *sigB* show significantly reduced survival
238 (Ferreira et al., 2001, Oliver et al., 2010). Moreover, σ^B also contributes to the
239 transcription of the *prfA* gene which positively regulates virulence genes as *plcA* and *hly*,
240 thus interconnecting stress response and virulence gene expression (Kazmierczak et al.,
241 2003, Kazmierczak et al., 2006, Ollinger et al., 2009, Chaturongakul et al., 2008).

242 Another molecular response of *L. monocytogenes* that provides oxidative stress
243 adaptation is the synthesis of cold shock proteins (Csp) (Loepfe et al., 2010). Csp also
244 contribute to the expression regulation of *plcA* and *hly* genes through the control of *prfA*
245 gene expression (Eshwar et al., 2017). Therefore, E-beam could produce the induced
246 expression of *plcA* and *hly* genes as a consequence of the increase of *sigB*-expression
247 and, possibly, the Csp-response.

248 However, in cases of stress produced by other agents, the genetic expression shows a
249 higher variability. Alía et al. (2019) reported that the presence of NaCl at the usual levels
250 of dry-cured ham and a_w between 0.94 and 0.92 decreased the expression of the virulence

251 genes *plcA*, *hly* and *iap* although these conditions favoured the expression of the *sigB*.
252 Mataragas et al. (2015) performed a study with fermented sausages and reported that
253 although adaptation to acid and osmotic stress increased *sigB* expression, this was not
254 associated with an increase in *prfA* expression. In other non-thermal technologies such as
255 high hydrostatic pressures (HHP), it has been described that the resulting stress causes
256 strong suppression of genes such as *sigB* and *prfA* (Bowman et al., 2008).

257 The *iap* gene is the one that encodes protein P60, a murein hydrolase responsible for the
258 remodelling of the cell wall peptidoglycan during bacterial division. It is a surface protein
259 that enables *Listeria* to adhere to any type of cell, so it is essential in its invasive capacity
260 (Pucciarelli et al., 2007). P60 also participates in *Listeria* intracellular movement and
261 cell-to-cell spread of as it is necessary for actin assembly (Pilgrim et al., 2003). The
262 regulation of the *iap* gene is independent of the expression of the *prfA* gene (Vázquez-
263 Boland et al., 2001) and *sigB* gene (Kim et al., 2005); σ^B contributes to the *L.*
264 *monocytogenes* invasiveness primarily by directly controlling the expression of the *inlA*
265 and *inlB* genes, rather than through indirect effects regulated by PrfA (Kim et al., 2005).
266 It has been reported that *iap* transcription is induced by exposure of *L. monocytogenes* to
267 acid and osmotic stress situations (Olesen et al., 2009). The results obtained in this work
268 showed an increase in the GER of *iap* gene also related to the applied E-beam dose. The
269 E-beam treatment may induce the *iap* gene expression in *L. monocytogenes* but, to date,
270 the mechanisms explaining the response to this stress have not been described.

271 Overall, the GER did not vary with the time of storage, although it was observed a trend
272 to increase as the days of storage elapse. Only significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) were
273 observed when treatment at 3 kGy was applied, with the highest expression observed on
274 day 30. Montiel et al. (2019) reported a down-regulation trend of some *L. monocytogenes*
275 virulence genes (*prfA*, *gbuB*, *lmo1421*, *lmo2434*, and *lmo0669*) in presence of enterocin
276 and *Enterococcus faecalis* in dry-cured ham stored for 7 days at 7°C. Makariti et al.
277 (2015) evaluated the response of *L. monocytogenes* to different pH and NaCl
278 combinations and reported a *sigB* and *prfA* up-regulation after 6 days of storage at 7°C.
279 These authors related the gene expression variations to the habituation of the pathogen to
280 the condition of the experiments.

281 There was not significant effect of storage temperature on the GER of the genes targeted
282 by this work. Contrary, Duodu et al. (2010) described that exposure to abuse temperature
283 conditions (20°C) might influence the virulence potential of *L. monocytogenes* strains in

284 salmon. Rantsiou et al. (2012) studied the influence of common (4°C) and abuse (12°C)
285 storage temperature on the expression of *sigB*, *hly*, *iap*, and *plcA* in several foods and
286 observed variability related to the *L. monocytogenes* strain, the food matrix and the
287 storage temperature. Alía et al. (2019), using dry-cured ham model systems contaminated
288 with *Listeria*, reported that *hly* and *iap* genes were more overexpressed at 15°C than at
289 7°C, while the *plcA* gene behaved contrarily.

290 The present work constitutes, to our knowledge, the first description of stress-response
291 and virulence gene expression in *L. monocytogenes* sublethally injured by E-beam. It is
292 possible that this damage could lead to cross-protection of survivors from stresses
293 commonly used as hurdles in the food industry. Ivy et al. (2012) reported that *L.*
294 *monocytogenes* adapted to cold temperatures improves its ability to overcome an adverse
295 acidity condition. In the same way, listeria that previously grow in acid or osmotic stress
296 conditions show a higher resistance against other stress such as thermal shock, osmotic
297 shock and alcoholic or oxidative stress (Phan-Thanh et al., 2000, Bergholz et al., 2012).
298 Even a short time (30 min) of pre-exposure to alkali (pH 9.0) and osmotic (0.3 M NaCl)
299 stresses improved the *L. monocytogenes* resistance to sublethal concentrations of bile salt
300 (Zhang et al., 2011). HHP also induces cross-resistance to heat, acid, and oxidative stress
301 (Karatzas and Bennik, 2002). However, our results would seem to indicate that after
302 resisting E-beam treatment this pathogen would not have acquired greater protection
303 against the adverse conditions of dry-cured ham since, as described above, its death rate
304 was similar to that of non-irradiated microorganisms during storage.

305 Although this treatment is efficient enough to eliminate the usual listerial contamination
306 from foods, from a practical point of view, the findings of this study may be particularly
307 interesting, for example, to design a combination of strategies to eliminate *L.*
308 *monocytogenes* reducing the minimum dose required (Ahn et al., 2018). Our results
309 highlight the importance of ensuring the application of proper E-beam treatments and
310 thus avoiding the survival of resilient and, as might be suggested from this study, more
311 virulent microorganisms.

312 **4. Conclusions**

313 The applied doses in this work allow reducing the *L. monocytogenes* cells number in dry-
314 cured ham under usual conditions until a safe level. The Gene Expression Rates (GERs)
315 of stress-response (*sigB*) and virulence (*plcA*, *hly* and *iap*) genes of the sublethally
316 injured cells increase with the E-beam dose, but they were not or slightly affected by

317 storage temperature and time, respectively. However, this enhanced adaptation ability
318 was insufficient to resist the listericidal effect of the environmental conditions of dry-
319 cured ham. Studies such as this need to be assessed as the over-expression of virulence
320 genes of this pathogen are of public health interest.

321

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328

329 **Conflicts of interest**

330 No potential conflict of interest is disclosed.

331

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Table 1

Counts of *Listeria monocytogenes* S4-2 (Log cfu/g \pm SD) survivors in dry-cured ham slices untreated (0 kGy) and treated with different E-beam doses of 1, 2 and 3 kGy at different days (0, 7, 15 and 30) during storage at 7°C.

Doses	Day 0	Day 7	Day 15	Day 30
0 kGy	7.91 \pm 0.06 ^{A,a}	7.76 \pm 0.01 ^{A,b}	7.65 \pm 0.20 ^{A,b,c}	7.21 \pm 0.10 ^{A,d}
1 kGy	6.78 \pm 0.16 ^{B,a}	6.82 \pm 0.12 ^{B,a}	6.17 \pm 0.21 ^{B,b}	5.88 \pm 0.19 ^{B,c}
2 kGy	5.33 \pm 0.08 ^{C,a}	4.91 \pm 0.12 ^{C,b}	4.72 \pm 0.38 ^{C,b}	4.30 \pm 0.02 ^{C,c}
3 kGy	3.30 \pm 0.06 ^{D,a}	2.79 \pm 0.02 ^{D,b}	2.50 \pm 0.09 ^{D,c}	1.86 \pm 0.11 ^{D,d}

SD, standard deviation.

^{A,B,C,D} Values in the same column with different letters are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

^{a,b,c,d} Values in the same row with different letters are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

Legend of figures

Fig. 1. Gene expression rate (GER) of *sigB*, *plcA*, *hly* and *iap* genes of *L. monocytogenes* in dry-cured ham slices untreated (0 kGy) and treated (1, 2 and 3 kGy) at different days (0: grey, 7: striped, 15: black and 30: white) during storage at 7 and 15°C.

GER = Log [gene copies/(cfu/g)]

^{A,B,C,D} Values in the same dose with different letters are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

^{a,b,c,d} Values in the same day with different letters are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

Figure

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